

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17871968

MEDIATING ROLE OF LIFE SATISFACTION IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL DEPENDENCE AND AMBIVALENT SEXISM AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

Marianne Mamani-Aedo^{1*}, Yabarit Rufasto-Torrealva², Carlos Pérez-Lara³

¹College of Social Sciences, Department of Psychology, Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Email: mmamaniae9@ucvvirtual.edu.pe, Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6127-3297>

²College of Social Sciences, Department of Psychology, Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Email: yrufastot@ucvvirtual.edu.pe, Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1464-5961>

³College of Social Sciences, Department of Psychology, Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Email: cperezla@ucvvirtual.edu.pe, Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5712-2186>

Received: 02/11/2025
Accepted: 15/11/2025

Corresponding Author: Marianne Mamani-Aedo
(mmamaniae9@ucvvirtual.edu.pe)

ABSTRACT

Purpose The study aimed to determine whether life satisfaction mediates the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism among university students in Trujillo. This research contributes to the achievement of SDG number 3: health and well-being. *Methodology*. The design was correlational quantitative, with a sample of 107 participants. The instruments used were the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS), the Emotional Dependence Questionnaire (CDE), and the Ambivalent Sexism Inventory (ISA). *Results* The results show that life satisfaction acts as a significant mediator in the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism ($p < .01$). Furthermore, there is a significant inverse correlation between life satisfaction and emotional dependence ($r = -0.37, p < .05$), and a significant negative correlation between life satisfaction and ambivalent sexism ($r = -0.46, p < .05$). Additionally, a significant positive correlation was found between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism ($r = 0.40, p < .05$). *Implications for research and practice*. In conclusion, life satisfaction acts as a significant mediator between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism; low levels of life satisfaction are associated with higher levels of emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism."

KEYWORDS: Life Satisfaction, Emotional Dependence, Ambivalent Sexism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mental health has been recognized as a global concern of significant importance, underscored by the World Health Organization (2022), which highlights the high incidence of mental disorders and an alarming suicide mortality rate, with over 58% of these deaths occurring before the age of 50. This scenario emphasizes the urgent need to address mental health comprehensively, as outlined in Sustainable Development Goal 3, which aims for physical, mental, and social well-being, extending beyond the mere absence of disease. Within this framework, life satisfaction emerges as an essential component of overall well-being, influenced by various personal, social, and cultural factors (Arias et al., 2018; Urrelo & Huamani, 2019; Ferreyros, 2021; Lagarda et al., 2022; Mikulic et al., 2019; Vinaccia & Parada, 2019). Therefore, it is crucial to explore and highlight the connection between the studied variables and overall well-being, and how life satisfaction serves as a mediator in the relationship between the other two variables.

Emotional dependence, defined as an extreme need for affection and attachment towards others, is directly related to the emotional and mental well-being of individuals. Since it is linked to emotional health, emotional dependence represents an obstacle to achieving a state of comprehensive well-being (Perez & Velazquez, 2022).

Ambivalent sexism, encompassing both hostile and benevolent attitudes towards women, affects the social and emotional health of individuals, particularly women, by perpetuating gender inequalities and stereotypes that may limit personal and professional development. These sexist attitudes contribute to a social environment that does not favor overall well-being, hindering the equality and mutual respect necessary for adequate social health (Lopez, García & Montero, 2019).

Regarding life satisfaction, it is a subjective measure of overall well-being, integrating personal evaluations of quality of life in relation to one's own expectations and circumstances. A high level of life satisfaction is associated with better mental and emotional health and is a key indicator of overall well-being. Life satisfaction reflects the fulfillment of basic needs and personal achievement (Gómez et al., 2023). Similarly, emotional dependence, defined as an extreme need for affection and attachment towards others (Rodríguez-de la Torre & Peña, 2022), and ambivalent sexism, which includes both hostile and benevolent attitudes towards women (Lampert, 2018; Cortés et al., 2022), are factors that have been studied in relation to life satisfaction.

However, most previous research has focused on exploring these variables in isolation or within specific contexts, such as the studies by Ponce et al. (2019), Mamani & Belizario (2022), and Aleán (2022), which focused on the relationship between emotional dependence and life satisfaction, or the work of Rollero et al. (2023), which examined the connection between ambivalent sexism and life satisfaction in Europe. Nevertheless, there is a gap in the literature regarding the interrelationship of these three variables collectively.

This study stands out from previous research by addressing this gap and proposing an integrative model that examines how life satisfaction may mediate the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism within the specific context of undergraduate students in Peru (Aleán, 2022; Mamani & Belizario, 2022; Ponce et al., 2019; Rollero et al., 2023). Unlike previous studies that have treated these variables separately, this work will investigate whether life satisfaction acts as a mediator in the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism, providing a more comprehensive and applicable understanding of the studied population's reality. This novel approach will allow for a more integrated understanding of the interaction of these factors in the well-being of students, a group facing significant challenges in their personal and social development.

The justification for this study lies in its theoretical and practical contributions. Theoretically, it will expand existing knowledge by integrating these variables into a single analytical model. Practically, it will offer direct implications for the development of interventions that promote the emotional and social well-being of university students. Methodologically, a rigorous research process will be conducted, providing relevant and applicable data to the reality of the studied population. The overall purpose of this research is to interrelate the variables of life satisfaction, emotional dependence, and ambivalent sexism. Socially, the development of this study will benefit undergraduate university students by addressing everyday problems that negatively affect their social well-being.

Given all the information presented, the following research question emerges: How does life satisfaction mediate the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism among university students? This question seeks to explore the dynamics between these variables and aims to uncover the potential mediating role of life satisfaction in influencing the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism.

The primary objective of this work is to verify whether life satisfaction mediates the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism in undergraduate university students. Specific objectives include identifying levels of emotional dependence, life satisfaction, and ambivalent sexism, as well as examining whether life satisfaction plays a mediating role between these variables. The study not only fills a significant gap in existing research but also provides valuable tools for improving the social and emotional well-being of students, contributing to their integral development in an increasingly challenging context.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Design

This quantitative, non-experimental study focuses on the numerical measurement of variables without manipulating them (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018; Calderón & Alzamora, 2020). It is a correlational study, allowing for the analysis of relationships between variables through prior descriptive analysis (Arias, 2020). Additionally, it has an explanatory scope, aiming to understand causal relationships through mediation correlation analysis, exploring how a mediating variable influences the relationship between the independent and dependent variables to delve into underlying mechanisms (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018).

2.2. Sampling

The study employed a non-probabilistic self-selection sampling method, allowing participants to voluntarily enroll themselves. This method is appropriate in contexts where it is difficult to access a complete list of the target population and where voluntary participation is crucial for obtaining precise and relevant data (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018). The sample comprised 107 university students of both genders from the city of Trujillo. The eligibility criteria for participant selection included undergraduate university students from public and private educational institutions in Peru who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study and fell within the age range of 18 to 25 years, thereby ensuring the study's representativeness and relevance to the target population.

The sample size was calculated considering parameters such as effect size $f^2 = 0.15$, alpha error probability $\alpha = 0.05$, power $(1-\beta) = 0.95$, and number of predictors = 2 (Cooper, 2020). and for social sciences (Fritz & MacKinnon, 2007). These parameters are commonly accepted in social and psychological sciences studies, ensuring that the

sample is adequate to detect significant effects in the variables studied. While a larger sample size could provide more precise estimates, the current size was sufficient to explore the specific relationships outlined in this study (Fritz & MacKinnon, 2007). Previous studies have successfully used similar sample sizes, demonstrating their ability to yield valid and reliable results in research with comparable characteristics.

2.3. Instrument And Data Collection

Data collection was conducted in several phases. Initially, appropriate instruments for each variable were selected. Three questionnaires were used for data collection, a common tool in research that allows systematic collection of statistical data (Oliván et al., 2021).

1. *Life Satisfaction (Variable X)*: Measured using the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) created by Diener et al. (1985) and adapted by Nieto et al. (2020) in Peru. The instrument has 5 items evaluated through a single dimension, satisfaction, comprising 5 indicators. This scale demonstrates adequate psychometric properties with a good reliability evidenced by a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = .745$.
2. *Emotional Dependence (Variable M)*: Measured using the Emotional Dependence Questionnaire by Lemos and Londoño (2006), adapted by Ventura and Caycho (2019). This scale has 23 items across 6 dimensions: Separation Anxiety, Partner's Affective Expression, Modification of Plans, Fear of Loneliness, Boundary Expression, and Attention Seeking. This instrument shows adequate reliability evidenced by a McDonald's Omega of $\Omega = .93$.
3. *Ambivalent Sexism (Variable Y)*: Measured using the Ambivalent Sexism Inventory (ASI) by Glick and Fiske (1996), adapted by Flores (2019). This test includes two dimensions, hostile sexism and benevolent sexism, with a reliability evidenced by a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = .85$.

Necessary formats for the instruments to be applied were also prepared, including informed consent and a sociodemographic form. Clear instructions were given on how to complete the instruments, emphasizing the confidentiality of the results. Participants were allowed to decide voluntarily if they wanted to participate. Finally, a database was created with the obtained information for subsequent analysis.

2.4. Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics: A descriptive analysis was conducted using distribution and frequency tables for the variables and their corresponding dimensions. Measures of central tendency such as mean and measures of dispersion such as standard deviation were used.

Inferential Statistics: A differential analysis was performed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. For the analysis of indirect effects in the mediation model, SPSS software with the PROCESS 4.2 add-on and JAMOVI were used.

2.5. Ethical Considerations

The study followed the ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association (2020) and the ethical standards of the College of Psychologists of Peru (2018). The validity and reliability of the data were ensured, plagiarism was avoided, and informed consent from participants or their legal representatives was obtained.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Descriptive Analysis

In Table 1, it can be observed that emotional dependence exists at a low level at 42% (n = 45), followed by a very low level at 36% (n = 39). Additionally, the dimension of attention seeking shows a predominance at a low level with 44% (n = 47), followed by an average level at 25% (n = 27). Fear of loneliness predominates at a high level with 58% (n = 62), followed by a very low level at 19% (n = 20). The dimension of separation anxiety shows 52% (n = 56) at a low level and 28% (n = 30) at a very low level. The boundary expression dimension has 46% (n = 49) at a very low level, followed by 35% (n = 37) at an average level. In the modification of plans dimension, a low level predominates at 39% (n = 42), followed by a very low level at 36% (n = 38). Finally, in the affective expression dimension, a low level predominates at 42% (n = 45), followed by a very low level at 32% (n = 34).

Table 1: Distribution And Frequency of the Emotional Dependence Variable and Its Dimensions.

Levels	SAN		PAE		MOP		FOL		BEX		ASE		Emotional Dependence	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Very High	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	0	4	4	2	2	2	2
High	7	7	11	10	9	8	7	7	17	16	6	6	8	7
Average	11	10	15	14	16	15	18	17	37	35	27	25	13	12
Low	56	52	45	42	42	39	62	58	49	46	47	44	45	42
Very Low	30	28	34	32	38	36	20	19	0	0	25	23	39	36

Note. N=107. SAN = Separation Anxiety, PAE = Partner's Affective Expression, MOP = Modification of Plans, FOL = Fear of Loneliness, BEX = Boundary Expression, ASE = Attention Seeking.

Table 2: Distribution And Frequency of the Life Satisfaction Variable.

Levels	Life Satisfaction	
	n	%
High	51	48
Medium	39	36
Low	17	16

Note. N=107. Life Satisfaction Is Unidimensional.

Table 2 shows the distribution and frequency of the life satisfaction variable among study participants. Out of 107 participants, 48% (n = 51) report a high level of life satisfaction. A 36% (n = 39) fall into the medium level of satisfaction. Finally, 16% (n = 17) report a low level of life satisfaction. These data indicate that the majority of participants, 84%,

experience life satisfaction levels ranging from moderate to high, while a significant minority, 16%, show dissatisfaction with their lives. Life satisfaction is considered unidimensional, measuring a single dimension of the participants' overall satisfaction with their lives.

Table 3: Distribution And Frequency of the Ambivalent Sexism Variable and Its Dimensions.

Levels	HSEX		BSEX		Ambivalent Sexism	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
High	21	20	21	20	21	20
Trend High	13	12	19	18	15	14
Moderate	16	15	19	18	18	17
Trend Low	7	7	12	11	10	9
Low	50	47	36	34	43	40

Note. N=107. HSEX = Hostile Sexism, BSEX = Benevolent Sexism

Table 3 shows the distribution and frequency of

the ambivalent sexism variable and its dimensions.

Regarding ambivalent sexism in general, 20% (n = 21) of participants are at a high level, while 40% (n = 43) are at a low level. In the hostile sexism dimension (HSEX), 20% (n = 21) of participants are at a high level, while 47% (n = 50) are at a low level. For benevolent sexism (BSEX), 20% (n = 21) of participants are at a high level, and 34% (n = 36) are at a low level. These results suggest that although a considerable proportion of participants show low levels of ambivalent sexism and its dimensions, a significant minority presents high levels.

Table 4 presents the results of the correlation test between various variables and dimensions, providing a detailed view of their relationships.

Table 4: Pearson's R Correlation Test.

Variables and Dimensions	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	2	3	3.1	3.2.
1. Emotional Dependence	-										
1.1. Separation Anxiety	0.956***	-									
1.2. Affective Expression	0.857***	0.763***	-								
1.3. Attention Seeking	0.723***	0.683***	0.593***	-							
1.4. Boundary Expression	0.769***	0.729***	0.525***	0.4***	-						
1.5. Plan Modification	0.865***	0.774***	0.72***	0.568***	0.585***	-					
1.6. Fear of Loneliness	0.791***	0.712***	0.566***	0.462***	0.701***	0.627***	-				
2. Life Satisfaction	-0.372***	-0.344***	-0.343***	-0.295***	-0.196*	-0.379***	-0.265**	-			
3. Sexism	0.403***	0.39***	0.338***	0.365***	0.204*	0.382***	0.308***	-0.466***	-		
3.1. Hostile Sexism	0.256**	0.262**	0.181	0.302**	0.099	0.246**	0.183	-0.396***	0.926***	-	
3.2. Benevolent Sexism	0.497***	0.466***	0.456***	0.37***	0.287**	0.468***	0.396***	-0.461***	0.901***	0.671***	-

Note. N = 107

*p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Life satisfaction shows negative correlations with emotional dependence (r = -0.372, p < 0.001) and all its subdimensions. The strongest negative correlation is with "Plan Modification" (r = -0.379, p < 0.001), suggesting that higher emotional dependence is associated with lower life satisfaction. This finding underscores the importance of addressing emotional dependence to improve individuals' overall life satisfaction and suggests that life satisfaction could be playing a mediating role in this relationship.

Ambivalent sexism, as a general variable, shows a positive correlation with emotional dependence (r = 0.403, p < 0.001) and its subdimensions, indicating that higher emotional dependence is associated with higher levels of sexism. Within the dimensions of sexism, "Benevolent Sexism" has a higher correlation with emotional dependence (r = 0.497, p < 0.001)

Emotional dependence, as the main variable, shows very strong correlations with its subdimensions. The highest correlation is observed with "Separation Anxiety" (r = 0.956, p < 0.001), indicating that as emotional dependence increases, so does separation anxiety. Additionally, emotional dependence is strongly correlated with "Affective Expression" (r = 0.857, p < 0.001), "Plan Modification" (r = 0.865, p < 0.001), and "Fear of Loneliness" (r = 0.791, p < 0.001), highlighting the interconnectedness of these dimensions.

3.1. Inferential Analysis

compared to "Hostile Sexism" (r = 0.256, p < 0.01). This suggests that emotional dependence may be more closely related to benevolent sexist attitudes than hostile ones, and that life satisfaction could be mediating these relationships.

The dimensions of "Hostile Sexism" and "Benevolent Sexism" are highly correlated with each other (r = 0.671, p < 0.001), suggesting that both types of sexism tend to coexist in individuals. These findings indicate the need for interventions aimed at reducing emotional dependence not only to improve life satisfaction but also to mitigate sexist attitudes, especially those of a benevolent nature. Life satisfaction emerges as a potential key mediator in the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism in the studied university student population.

Table 5: Mediation Analysis: Life Satisfaction on Emotional Dependence and Ambivalent Sexism.

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
			LL	UL	
Efecto Indirecto X sobre Y	0.101	0.0339	0.0348	0.168	0.003
Efecto Directo X sobre Y	0.197	0.0645	0.0711	0.324	0.002
Efecto total X sobre Y	0.299	0.0645	0.1724	0.425	< .001

Note: N=107 SE = Standard Error; CI = Confidence Interval, LL = Lower Limit, UL = Upper Limit.

The indirect effect (a x b) of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism through life satisfaction has an estimated value of 0.101, with a standard error (SE)

of 0.0339. The 95% confidence interval (CI) for this indirect effect ranges from 0.0348 to 0.168, with a p-value of 0.003. This indicates that the effect is

statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Practically, this means that part of the influence of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism is explained by its impact on life satisfaction.

The direct effect (c') of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism, not mediated by life satisfaction, is 0.197, with a standard error of 0.0645. The 95% confidence interval for this direct effect ranges from 0.0711 to 0.324, with a p -value of 0.002, indicating that this effect is also statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that even without considering life satisfaction, emotional dependence has a significant impact on ambivalent sexism.

The total effect (c) of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism, combining both direct and indirect effects, is 0.299, with a standard error of 0.0645. The 95% confidence interval for this total effect extends from 0.1724 to 0.425, with a statistically significant p -value ($p < 0.001$). This total effect represents the sum of the direct impact of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism and the indirect impact through life satisfaction.

These results indicate that life satisfaction plays a significant mediating role in the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism. The significant indirect effect ($a \times b = 0.101$, $p = 0.003$) shows that improving life satisfaction could reduce the influence of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism. At the same time, the significant direct effect ($c' = 0.197$, $p = 0.002$) indicates that emotional dependence has a considerable impact on ambivalent sexism even without the mediation of life satisfaction. Together, these findings highlight the importance of life satisfaction as a key factor in the dynamics between emotional dependence and sexist attitudes among university students.

4. DISCUSSION

The aim of the present study was to determine whether life satisfaction mediates the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism among university students. The findings from the mediation analysis provide significant insights into this relationship, highlighting the importance of life satisfaction as a mediating variable. The results indicate that life satisfaction significantly mediates the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism. The indirect effect ($a \times b$) of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism through life satisfaction was significant, with an estimated value of 0.101 ($SE = 0.0339$, 95% CI [0.0348, 0.168], $p = 0.003$). This suggests that part of the influence of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism is explained by its impact on life satisfaction.

Practically, higher levels of emotional dependence are associated with lower life satisfaction, which in turn is related to higher levels of ambivalent sexism.

The direct effect (c') of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism, independent of life satisfaction, was also significant, with an estimated value of 0.197 ($SE = 0.0645$, 95% CI [0.0711, 0.324], $p = 0.002$). This indicates that even without considering life satisfaction, emotional dependence has a significant impact on ambivalent sexism. The total effect (c) of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism, which combines both direct and indirect effects, was 0.299 ($SE = 0.0645$, 95% CI [0.1724, 0.425], $p < 0.001$), further reinforcing the substantial relationship between these variables.

The negative correlation between life satisfaction and emotional dependence ($r = -0.372$, $p < 0.05$) suggests that individuals with higher emotional dependence tend to have lower life satisfaction. Additionally, the negative correlation between life satisfaction and ambivalent sexism ($r = -0.46$, $p < 0.05$) indicates that lower life satisfaction is associated with higher levels of ambivalent sexism. These findings are consistent with previous research indicating that life satisfaction is a critical factor in mitigating negative emotional and behavioral outcomes (Pérez et al., 2022; Urrelo & Huamani, 2019).

The positive correlation between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism ($r = 0.40$, $p < 0.05$) supports the notion that individuals with high emotional dependence are more likely to exhibit sexist attitudes. Interestingly, within the dimensions of ambivalent sexism, emotional dependence correlated more strongly with benevolent sexism ($r = 0.497$, $p < 0.05$) than with hostile sexism ($r = 0.256$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that emotionally dependent individuals may lean more towards benevolent sexist attitudes, which perceive women as needing protection and affection, rather than hostile sexist attitudes, which view women as inferior or ineffective in authoritative roles (Cortés et al., 2022; Lampert, 2018).

These findings highlight the complex interplay between emotional dependence, life satisfaction, and ambivalent sexism. The mediating role of life satisfaction suggests that interventions aimed at improving life satisfaction could potentially reduce the impact of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism. This has practical implications for designing programs and policies in educational settings to enhance student well-being and promote gender equality (Espinoza & Sandoval, 2021; Sencara, 2021).

These results underscore the importance of

addressing emotional dependence and improving life satisfaction to mitigate ambivalent sexism among university students. By enhancing life satisfaction, it is possible to reduce both emotional dependence and the prevalence of sexist attitudes, contributing to a healthier and more equitable social environment. Future research should explore the underlying mechanisms of these relationships and examine the effectiveness of specific interventions in different cultural and educational contexts (Mikulic *et al.*, 2019; Vinaccia & Parada, 2019).

5. LIMITATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Despite the significant findings of this study, several limitations must be considered. First, the study sample consists solely of university students, which limits the generalizability of the results to other populations. Specific cultural and contextual factors of this sample may influence the results; therefore, future studies should include more diverse and representative samples. Moreover, data were collected through self-reports, which may introduce social desirability or selective memory biases. Participants might have responded in a socially acceptable manner rather than reflecting their true feelings and behaviors. Future studies could benefit from using more varied and less bias-prone data collection methods, such as in-depth interviews or observational methods.

Despite the limitations, the results of this study have important practical and theoretical implications. Firstly, the finding that life satisfaction mediates the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism suggests that interventions aimed at improving life satisfaction could positively impact reducing sexist attitudes and mitigating emotional dependence. Well-being programs in universities that promote life satisfaction and healthy emotional relationship management could be especially beneficial. Secondly, the results underscore the need to address emotional dependence as a significant factor in the development of sexist attitudes. Educational strategies that teach emotional independence skills and foster self-esteem can help reduce both emotional dependence and sexist attitudes, promoting a culture of equality and respect in educational settings.

Theoretically, this study contributes to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence of the relationship between emotional dependence, life satisfaction, and ambivalent sexism in a Peruvian university population. The findings support the theory that life satisfaction can act as an important

mediator in the relationships between emotional and behavioral variables. Future studies should further explore the underlying mechanisms and consider other mediating or moderating variables that may influence these relationships. This study also highlights the importance of life satisfaction in the dynamics between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism and suggests that interventions focused on improving the overall well-being of university students may be effective in promoting healthier and more equitable attitudes.

6. CONCLUSION

This study explored the mediating role of life satisfaction in the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism among undergraduate university students. The results provide clear evidence that life satisfaction acts as a significant mediator in this relationship, which has important implications for understanding and addressing these phenomena in educational contexts.

First, it was found that emotional dependence has a direct and significant influence on ambivalent sexism. This finding suggests that individuals with high levels of emotional dependence are more likely to have sexist attitudes. Additionally, the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism was stronger in the dimension of benevolent sexism than in hostile sexism. This indicates that emotional dependence may be more closely related to attitudes that perceive women as needing protection and care, rather than attitudes that view them as inferior.

Second, life satisfaction showed a significant negative correlation with both emotional dependence and ambivalent sexism. This suggests that increasing life satisfaction could be an effective strategy to reduce both emotional dependence and sexist attitudes. The significant indirect effect of emotional dependence on ambivalent sexism through life satisfaction reinforces the idea that life satisfaction is a crucial factor in this dynamic.

Third, the findings have important practical implications. Interventions designed to improve life satisfaction could help mitigate the negative effects of emotional dependence and reduce sexist attitudes among university students. This could be achieved through well-being and emotional education programs that promote self-esteem and emotional independence, as well as the promotion of a culture of equality and respect.

This study highlights the importance of life satisfaction as a key mediator in the relationship between emotional dependence and ambivalent

sexism. By improving life satisfaction, the prevalence of sexist attitudes can be reduced, and healthier emotional relationships can be promoted among undergraduate university students. Future studies

should continue exploring these mechanisms in different contexts and populations to develop effective and evidence-based interventions.

REFERENCES

- Aleán, M. (2022). *Relación entre la satisfacción en las relaciones de pareja, las creencias románticas y el sexismo ambivalente en los adultos jóvenes del norte de Colombia: comparación de personas con y sin pareja* [Tesis de maestría, Universidad del Norte] Colombia. <http://hdl.handle.net/10584/11001>
- Arias, E. (2020). Investigación correlacional. Economía. <https://economipedia.com/definiciones/investigacion-correlacional.html>
- Arias, W., Huamani, J. y Caycho, T. (2018). Satisfacción con la vida en escolares de la ciudad de Arequipa. *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 6(1), 351-407. <https://dx.doi.org/10.20511/pyr2018.v6n1.206>
- Calderón, J. & Alzamora, L. (2020). Diseños de investigación para tesis de posgrado. *Revista peruana de psicología y trabajo social*, 7 (2). <http://revistas.uigv.edu.pe/index.php/psicologia/article/view/660>
- Cooper, H. (2020). *Informes de investigaciones cuantitativas en psicología: cómo cumplir con los estándares de informes de artículos de revistas estilo APA (2ª ed.)*. Asociación Estadounidense de Psicología. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0000178-000>
- Cortés, L., Sánchez, M., & Mézquita, Y. (2022). Sexismo, ideología de género y apoyo a premisas socioculturales en estudiantes de educación superior. *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, 6(2), 1315-1342. https://doi.org/10.37811/cl_rcm.v6i2.1956
- Espinoza, O. & Sandoval, A. (2021). Sexismo ambivalente y dependencia emocional en estudiantes Universitarios de Lima Metropolitana. [Thesis, Universidad César Vallejo]. <https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/handle/20.500.12692/75657>
- EsSalud. (2021). Essalud alerta que mujeres con dependencia emocional son más propensas a ser víctimas de violencia de sus parejas. <http://noticias.essalud.gob.pe/?inno-noticia=essalud-alerta-que-mujeres-con-dependencia-emocional-son-mas-propensas-a-ser-victimas-de-violencia-de-sus-parejas>
- Ferreiros, N., & Padilla, A. (2021). *Satisfacción laboral y satisfacción con la vida en docentes de educación inicial de la UGEL 01 de Lima, 2020* [Thesis, Universidad César Vallejo]. <https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/handle/20.500.12692/61938>
- Flores, L. (2019) *Propiedades psicométricas del inventario de sexismo ambivalente en estudiantes de dos universidades de Lima sur* [Thesis, Universidad César Vallejo, Universidad Autónoma del Perú]. <https://repositorio.autonoma.edu.pe/handle/20.500.13067/1915>
- Fritz, M. & Mackinnon, D. (2007). Mediation Analysis. *Annual Review of Psychology* 58(1):593-614. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/6823227_Mediation_Analysis
- Gómez, O., Zazueta, C., Santoyo, F., & Betanzos, F. (2023). Asociación entre creencias racionales e irracionales y la satisfacción con la vida: una revisión sistemática con meta-análisis. *Revista de Psicología y Ciencias del Comportamiento de la Unidad Académica de Ciencias Jurídicas y Sociales*, 14(2), 123-140
- Hernández-Sampieri, R. & Mendoza, C (2018). Metodología de la investigación. Las rutas cuantitativa, cualitativa y mixta. Editorial Mc Graw Hill Education, 1(5), 714 p. <https://doi.org/10.22201/fesc.20072236e.2019.10.18.6>
- Lagarda, A., Vera, J. & Tanori, J. (2022). Satisfacción con la vida y sus correlatos socio-personales en adolescentes de secundarias públicas de Sonora, México. *Revista Psicología*, 40 (1), 9-35. <https://doi.org/10.18800/psico.202201.001>
- Lampert, M. (2018). *Definición del concepto de "sexismo": influencia en el lenguaje, la educación y la violencia de género*. Biblioteca del Congreso Nacional de Chile: Asesoría Técnica Parlamentaria. https://obtienearchivo.bcn.cl/obtienearchivo?id=repositorio/10221/26147/1/BCN_definicion_sexismo_FINAL.pdf
- Lemos, M. & Londoño, N. (2006). Construcción y validación del cuestionario de dependencia emocional en población colombiana. *Redalyc*, 9 (2), 127-140. <https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/798/79890212.pdf>
- López, M., García, D., & Montero, I. (2019). El sexismo como constructo en psicología: una revisión de teorías e instrumentos. *Quaderns de psicología*, 21(3), e1523-e1523
- Mamani, P. & Belizario, Y. (2022). *Dependencia emocional, satisfacción con la vida y conductas de riesgo en adolescentes de una institución educativa del nivel secundario de la ciudad de Juliaca, 2022* [Thesis Universidad Peruana

- Unión] <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12840/6267>
- Mikulic, I., Crespi, M. & Caballero, R. (2019). Escala de satisfacción con la vida (SWLS): Estudio de las propiedades psicométricas en adultos de buenos aires. Anuario de investigaciones. Universidad de Buenos Aires. <https://www.psi.uba.ar/accesos.php?var=investigaciones/revistas/anuario/antiores/anuario26/rabajo.php&id=1085>
- Oliván, J., Cuenca, G., & Avilés, R. (2021). Evaluación de la investigación con encuestas en artículos publicados en revistas del área de Biblioteconomía y Documentación. *Revista Española De Documentación Científica*, 44 (2), 295. <https://doi.org/10.3989/redc.2021.2.1774>
- Organización Mundial de la Salud. (2021). *Comprender y abordar la violencia contra las mujeres: violencia de pareja*. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-RHR-12.36>
- Pérez, G., Reátegui, C., Vela, M., Aranda, J., & Revelo, S. (2022). Dependencia emocional como predictor de la violencia en el noviazgo en varones universitarios peruanos. *Revista Científica De Ciencias De La Salud*, 15 (2), 56 - 66. <https://doi.org/10.17162/rccs.v2i15.1893>
- Pérez, K. & Velásquez, L. (2022). *Relación existente entre la dependencia emocional y los vínculos de pareja contemporáneos en el discurso capitalista. Una revisión documental*. [Thesis, Corporación Universitaria Minuto de Dios]. <https://repository.uniminuto.edu/xmlui/handle/10656/17552>
- Pinar E. y Pinar G. (2021). Actitudes sexistas y satisfacción con la vida en estudiantes universitarios. *Ascepio*, 4(1), 4103. <https://doi.org/10.33309/2638-7697.040103>
- Ponce, C., Aiquipa, J., & Arbocó, M. (2019). Dependencia emocional, satisfacción con la vida y violencia de pareja en estudiantes universitarios. *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 7, 351-351. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20511/pyr2019.v7nSPE.351>
- Quiroz, I, Godínez, M., Jahuey, A., Montes, M., & Ortega Andrade, N. (2021). Autoestima y dependencia emocional en relaciones de pareja de estudiantes universitarios. *Educación y Salud Boletín Científico Instituto de Ciencias de la Salud Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo*, 9 (18), 91-98. <https://doi.org/10.29057/icsa.v9i18.6314>
- Rodríguez-de la Torre, R., & Peña, C. (2022). Dinámicas de la dependencia emocional en relaciones interpersonales: una revisión contemporánea. *Revista Internacional de Psicología Clínica y de la Salud*, 34 (2), 120-135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rips.2022.03.001>
- Rollero, C., Czepczor -Bernat, K., Fedi, A. et al. (2023). Satisfacción con la vida en Europa e Irán: el papel de la autoestima, la identificación de género y el sexismo ambivalente. *Curr Psychol*, 42, 23541-23554. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12144-022-03381-8>
- Sencara, R. (2021) *Dependencia emocional y sexismo ambivalente en jóvenes estudiantes víctimas y no víctimas de violencia de género en Lima Norte, 2021* [Thesis, Universidad César Vallejo]. <https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/handle/20.500.12692/78324>
- Tello, P., & Céspedes, D. (2023). Dependencia emocional y su relación con la resiliencia en estudiantes universitarios. *Ciencia Latina Revista Multidisciplinar*, 7 (1), 3189-3206. https://doi.org/10.37811/cl_rcm.v7i1.4650
- Urbiola, I., Estévez, A., Iruarrizaga, I., y Jauregui, P. (2017). Dependencia emocional en jóvenes: relación con la sintomatología ansiosa y depresiva, autoestima y diferencias de género. *Ansiedad y Estrés*, 23 (1), 6-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anyes.2016.11.003>
- Urrelo, A., & Huamani, J. (2019). Satisfacción con la vida y estilos de afrontamiento en adolescentes de colegios públicos en la ciudad de Arequipa. *Revista De Psicología*, 9 (2), 13-32. <https://revistas.ucsp.edu.pe/index.php/psicologia/article/view/394>
- Ventura, J. y Caycho, T. (2019). Análisis psicométrico de una escala de dependencia emocional en universitarios peruanos. *Revista de Psicología Universidad de Chile*. 25 (1). 1-17. <https://dx.doi.org/10.5354/0719-0581.2016.42453>
- Vinaccia Alpi, S., Parada, N., Quiceno, JM, Riveros Munévar, F. & Vera Maldonado, LA (2019). Escala de satisfacción con la vida (SWLS): análisis de validez, confiabilidad y baremos para estudiantes universitarios de Bogotá: Escala de satisfacción con la vida (SWLS): análisis de validez, confiabilidad y evaluación en estudiantes universitarios de Bogotá (Col) como muestra. *Psicogente*, 22 (42), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.17081/psico.22.42.3468>
- Zárate, N., Flores, P., Martínez, E., Alvarado, E., & Jiménez, C. (2022). Dependencia emocional en estudiantes de Medicina. *Revista Médica Herediana*, 33 (2), 128-132. <https://doi.org/10.20453/rmh.v33i2.4246>